

Studies in Chain Transfer. Part VII.* Polymerisation of Methyl Acrylate and Styrene

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Methyl acrylate has been polymerised in bulk using hydrogen peroxide as initiator at 50°, 60°, and 80°. The kinetic constants δ , C_{tr} and C_t have been evaluated and R_p is found to be proportional to $I^{0.5}$.

From the thermal polymerisation of methyl acrylate in solution, chain-transfer values for eighteen solvents have been determined. C_s values for some solvents in the polymerisation of methyl methacrylate and styrene, hitherto not reported, have also been evaluated. The trend of the C_s values with the nature of the solvent-monomer pair and radical reactivity has been discussed in detail.

In previous parts of this series, the values of chain-transfer constants with a large number of solvents in the polymerisation of methyl methacrylate¹, vinyl acetate², and acrylonitrile³ have been reported. This communication presents our results of similar studies with methyl acrylate in thermal polymerisation in different solvents and also in hydrogen peroxide-initiated polymerisation in bulk. Some new data for styrene and methyl methacrylate are presented for the sake of comparison.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental details regarding purification of monomers and solvents, hydrogen peroxide, polymerisation technique, etc. were essentially the same as described in the previous parts¹⁻⁴ with some modifications as necessitated by the nature of the monomer taken and of the polymer formed. Stabilised monomers, supplied by the Eastman Kodak Co., Rochester, N. Y. and National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, were washed free of inhibitors with alkali, dried, and fractionally distilled. All polymerisation experiments were carried out in sealed tubes at 50°, 60°, and 80° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). Polymerisation was never allowed to proceed beyond 5% conversion and the polymer samples were isolated by several precipitations with methanol or ethanol, followed by drying in a vacuum oven at 50° for at least 24 hours.

The average degree of polymerisation ($\bar{P}_n$) was determined by viscometric method, utilising the relation:

$$\bar{P}_n = K [\eta]^\alpha$$

* Part VI of the series: Khanna *et al.*, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1962, 56, 1927.

1. Basu *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1950, A202, 485; 1952, A214, 247.

2. Palit and Das, *ibid.*, 1954, A226, 82.

3. Das *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1955, A227, 262.

4. Nandi and Palit, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1955, 17, 65.

where $[\eta]$ is the intrinsic viscosity of the solution in decilitres per g. and K and α are constants for each polymer in benzene at 35°. The values of these constants used in the present investigation are $K=1769, 2810$, and 3258 and $\alpha=1.277, 1.32$, and 1.4 for polystyrene⁵, polymethyl methacrylate⁶, and polymethyl acrylate⁷ respectively.

Methyl acrylate, polymerised at 60° using hydrogen peroxide and benzoyl peroxide as initiator, showed typical induction period (Fig. 1). At all the temperatures (50°, 60°, and 80°), the rate of polymerisation (R_p) is proportional to $(I)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ in agreement with the usual equation:

$$R_p = K (I)^{\frac{1}{2}} (M)^{\alpha} \quad \dots (1)$$

where (I) and (M) are the initiator and monomer concentration respectively and K is a constant. Fig. 2 shows plots of R_p versus $I^{\frac{1}{2}}$ for the bulk polymerisation of methyl acrylate over the range 50-80°. These are linear as with methyl methacrylate⁸, styrene⁹, and other initiators and may indicate that the termination reaction is of second order.

FIG. 1. Peroxide-initiated polymerisation of methyl acrylate (5.54M) in methyl acetate at 60°.
 O— 14.00×10^{-3} moles/litre of H_2O_2 .
 ●— 19.20×10^{-3} moles/litre of benzoyl peroxide.

Evaluation of $\delta (= k_t^{\frac{1}{2}}/k_p)$.—The general equation for the average degree of polymerisation at bulk can be easily deduced as

$$1/\bar{P} = C_M + C_1^{[I]} / (M) + \delta^2 (R_p) / (M)^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

5. Gregg and Mayo, *Faraday Soc. Disc.*, 1947, 2, 328.

6. Baxendale *et al.*, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1946, 1, 237.

7. Sen *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 90.

8. Palit *et al.*, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1954, 14, 295.

9. Mayo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 2324; 1948, 70, 3639.

where $\bar{P}$ is the average degree of polymerisation; C_M and C_I are the transfer constants for monomer and initiator respectively. According to this equation, the plot of $1/\bar{P} - C_I^{1/2}/(M)$ against R_p should provide a straight line, from the slope of which δ can be determined. The results are recorded in Table I.

FIG. 2. Rate of polymerisation of methyl acrylate at diff. conc. as a function of H_2O_2 conc.

Curves 1-3 refer respectively to bulk at 80°, 60°, and 50°.

Curve 4 ⊕ — Butanol² 60°, $(S/M = 0.99)$
 „ 5 ⊕ — „ „ $(S/M = 3.75)$
 „ 5 ● — „ „ $(S/M = 8.88)$

TABLE I

Polymerisation of methyl acrylate in bulk (10.07 moles l⁻¹) in presence of H₂O₂ (I) at diff. temp.

Temp.	$(I) \times 10^3$ ^a (mole/litre).	$(1/\bar{P}) \times 10^5$ (mole/litre/sec.).	$R_p \times 10^5$.	δ .	$E_{(1/\delta)}$ (kcal.).	$C_M \times 10^5$.	E_{C_M} (kcal.).	C_I .	E_{C_I} (kcal.).
80°	140.0	5.53	340.00	0.82	8.42	1.30	6.03	0.29	5.28
	84.0	4.05	260.00						
	28.0	2.82	148.00						
	14.0	1.78	107.00						
	2.8	1.54	50.00						
60°	140.0	3.57	33.85	1.64	..	0.84	..	0.21	..
	84.0	2.33	24.60						
	28.0	1.72	10.00						
	14.0	1.02	8.63						
	2.8	0.68	4.18						
50°	140.0	2.29	5.21	2.40	..	0.57	..	0.14	..
	84.0	1.82	3.85						
	28.0	1.43	2.05						
	14.0	1.03	1.39						
	2.8	0.64	0.50						

TABLE II (contd.)

Solvents.	S/M.	$[\eta]$.	$10^4 \bar{P}$.	$10^4 \bar{C}_n$.	Solvents.	S/M.	$[\eta]$.	$10^4 \bar{P}$.	$10^4 \bar{C}_n$.
B. Styrene.									
None	0.00	2.90	1.450		Acetone	14.09	0.81	7.308	
Cyclohexane	0.30	1.66	2.050			6.26	1.18	4.375	4.01
	2.48	2.41	1.830	1.54		3.65	1.72	2.828	
	1.06	2.64	1.638			1.37	0.20	2.063	
Toluene	0.71	1.07	5.184		Methyl ethyl ketone	11.53	-0.38	10.440	
	4.32	1.05	2.082	3.81		3.12	0.66	9.249	
	2.52	1.86	3.530			2.29	0.06	3.054	
	1.08	2.38	1.867			1.28	1.34	3.869	14.04
Butanol ^b	11.20	0.91	6.377		Methyl isobutyl ketone	8.28	-0.66	9.610	
	3.02	1.25	3.965	4.04		3.07	1.12	4.891	10.14
	1.33	2.02	2.302			0.92	2.12	2.165	
	1.25	2.04	2.274		C. Methyl methacrylate.				
Butanol ^c	11.26	0.56	11.850						
	11.26	0.57	11.500						
	5.00	0.04	6.117		Cyclohexanol	9.25	0.66	6.160	
	2.92	1.34	3.800	0.30		4.11	1.01	3.513	5.87
	2.92	1.98	3.745			2.40	1.38	2.326	
	1.25	1.64	2.504			1.03	2.28	1.214	
	1.25	2.15	2.137						
Butanol	11.00	1.08	5.247	3.44	1-Methylcyclohexan-1-ol	8.76	0.70	4.980	4.78
	1.22	2.36	1.868			0.97	2.28	1.130	
Cyclohexanol	9.93	1.05	5.310		Cyclohexane	0.00	2.20	1.040	
	2.57	1.83	2.612	3.82		4.00	4.00	0.500	0.89
	1.10	2.15	2.172			2.30	4.30	0.450	
Acetic acid	4.88	1.01	1.450		Methylcyclohexane	7.65	1.25	2.651	2.56
	2.00	2.32	1.620	2.02		1.98	2.30	1.093	
						0.85	2.65	0.083	
Isobutyric acid	4.95	0.70	8.910		Hexane ^d	7.37	1.05	3.396	4.38
	2.39	1.01	3.680	14.00		1.31	2.73	0.945	4.38
	1.24	1.29	3.730			0.82	4.38	0.506	

TABLE III

Chain-transfer constants and related quantities.

Monomer.	CCl ₄		CBr ₄		CHCl ₃		DucSH		Triethylamine		k _p (60°).
	10 ⁴ C ₁	10 ³ K ₁	C ₂	10 ⁻³ K ₁	10 ⁴ C ₁	K ₁	C ₂	K ₁	10 ⁴ C ₁	K ₁	
Styrene (60°)	9009	1584	2.2016	3.87	5.899	9.856 × 10 ⁻³	22.0015	3872	71.017	124.96 × 10 ⁻³	176 ^{sec}
" (60°)	13439	4400	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
Methylmeth- acrylate (60°)	18.91	69.36	0.2716	1.00	7.431	27.269 × 10 ⁻³	0.6715	245.89	83.017	304.61 × 10 ⁻³	367 ^{mob}
" (60°)	23.91	154.20	..	..	14.001	90.3 × 10 ⁻³	..	..	..	..	..
Methyl acrylate (60°)	..	..	0.4116	8.57	..	..	1.69	3532	4.00017	83.60	2090 ^{mob}
" (60°)	13.23	535.20	..	..	21.44	887.3 × 10 ⁻³	..	..	..	..	..
Vinyl acetate (60°)	..	..	39.0016	1443	1251.80 ²	48.32	48.0015	1777 × 10 ²	3.70017	136.90	3700 ^{mob}
Acrylo- nitride (60°)	8.35	7.14	0.1917	0.16	56.403	41.38 × 10 ⁻³	..	..	59,00017	48.56	8419

Transfer with Monomer (C_M).— C_M was determined from the plot of $1/\bar{P}$ against R_p , C_M being the intercept. The values are also reported in Table I.

Transfer with Initiator (C_I).—Equation (2) can be written in the form

$$(1/\bar{P} - C_M)/(I) = C_I/(M) + K.M/R_p \quad \dots (3)$$

C_I was obtained from the plot of the left hand side against $1/R_p$ and reported in Table I.

Transfer with Solvent (C_S).— C_S was determined from the thermal polymerisation data from the relationship:

$$1/\bar{P} = C_S (S)/(M) + 1/\bar{P}_0$$

where $(S)/(M)$ is the mole ratio of the solvent to monomer and $\bar{P}_0$, the average degree of polymerisation in absence of a solvent. A plot of $1/\bar{P}$ vs. $(S)/(M)$ provides a straight line, the least square slope of which is taken as C_S .

The results of the measurement of chain-transfer constant in the polymerisation of methyl acrylate, styrene, and methyl methacrylate are summarised Table II.

Chain-transfer constants of the solvents CCl_4 , $CHCl_3$, CBr_4 , C_6H_5SH , and Et_3N in the polymerisation of the five monomers, viz., vinyl acetate, styrene, methyl methacrylate, methyl acrylate, and acrylonitrile, are presented in Table III. The absolute values of $k_{tr}S$, calculated from the known values of the propagation constants, have also been incorporated therein. Table IV shows how the ratio of the chain-transfer constants for a pair of solvents varies in the cases of the five monomers, mentioned above.

TABLE IV

Chain-transfer constants and related quantities.

	Acrylonitrile.	Methyl acrylate.	Methyl methacrylate.	Styrene.	Vinyl acetate.
C_{TEA}/C_{Tol}	1010	148	42	59	18.0
$10^{-3}C_{CBr_4}/C_{Tol}$	0.33	1.52	13.5	183	18.3
C_{TEA}/C_{CBr_4}	3.10	0.10	3.1×10^{-3}	3.2×10^{-4}	10^{-3}
C_{CBr_4}/C_{Tol}	0.967	1.20	3.71	4.72	6.0
C_{TEA}/C_{CHCl_3}	1050	..	11.10	12.50	3.0
C_{TEA}/C_{CCl_4}	6.9×10^3	..	4.40	0.079	Vary low
C_{RSH}/C_{Tol}	..	636	33.5×10^3	18.33×10^3	21×10^3
C_{CCl_4}/C_{Tol}	0.145	0.742(80°)	9.45(80°)	750	Very high
C_{CHCl_3}/C_{CCl_4}	6.63	1.62	0.39	6.30×10^{-4}	..

NB. TEA=triethylamine; Tol=toluene; RSH=nbutyl mercaptan.

DISCUSSION

The results show that, in general, the values of the chain-transfer constants for methyl acrylate are higher than the corresponding values for the monomers: styrene and methyl methacrylate. Gadkary and Kapur¹⁸ have reported the chain-transfer constants for a number of solvents in the benzoyl peroxide-initiated polymerisation of methyl acrylate. Their values have been compared with ours in Table II. The C_S values obtained by

Gadkary and Kapur¹⁸ are much higher than those obtained by us except in the cases of chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. We have already pointed out in our earlier publications¹⁻⁴ the limitations of obtaining C_s from the plot of $1/\bar{P}$ against S/M from catalysed polymerisation data. It has been clearly demonstrated that in the benzoyl peroxide-initiated polymerisation of methyl methacrylate^{1,18}, the presence of the peroxide affords values higher than those obtained from thermal polymerisation data and the value increases with the concentration of the initiator. The results of methyl acrylate, obtained by Gadkary and Kapur¹⁸, clearly show its similarity with methyl methacrylate and this might explain higher C_s values obtained by them.

Hydrocarbons generally have the lowest transfer constants, cyclohexane having the lowest value, but marked increase is observed for hexane⁹. Transfer with benzene is quite appreciable as is also found in the case of methyl methacrylate¹ and styrene⁹. For alkyl-benzenes, the transfer constant with methyl acrylate increases in the order: toluene < ethylbenzene < isopropylbenzene. The explanation based on the reactivity of benzylic hydrogen^{9,11} atoms in these solvents, advanced for other monomers, seems to be valid in this case also. In this connection it is admitted that one should really compare the activation energies rather than the transfer constants at a particular temperature, but most of the required data are not available.

The chain-transfer constants of alcohols, e.g., the butanol series, show a remarkable regularity in all the monomers, viz., styrene⁹, methyl methacrylate¹, vinyl acetate², acrylonitrile³, and methyl acrylate. The values of C_s increase in the order: BuOH¹ < BuOH² < BuOH³ < BuOH⁴. The reactivity of the α -hydrogen atom is the determining factor in these solvents also. It should be pointed out, however, that cyclohexanol, though a secondary alcohol, is not as efficient a transfer agent as BuOH⁴ in styrene and methyl methacrylate polymerisation.

Interesting digressions in the choice of solvents in methyl methacrylate polymerisation are cyclohexanol and 1-methylcyclohexan-1-ol. The chain-transfer constants for methyl methacrylate polymerisation in these two solvents (Table II), when compared with those in cyclohexane and methylcyclohexane, lead to an interesting conclusion. The transfer constant of cyclohexane (0.89×10^{-3}) is low on account of absence of any active hydrogen atom in the molecule. In methylcyclohexane (2.56×10^{-3}), the methyl group is attached to a tertiary carbon atom carrying the active hydrogen. Similar is the case for cyclohexanol (5.87×10^{-3}), where instead of the methyl group, there is a hydroxyl group. 1-Methylcyclohexan-1-ol, however, contains no such active tertiary hydrogen atom and so its transfer constant is expected to be approximately equal to that of cyclohexane provided that the hydroxyl groups take no part in the transfer reaction. The higher transfer constant for 1-methylcyclohexane-1-ol (4.78×10^{-3}) may therefore be attributed to the transfer reaction with the hydroxyl group.

Chain-transfer constants for ketones and aliphatic acids in the polymerisation of methyl acrylate and styrene follow the same sequence as those in the polymerisation of methyl methacrylate¹, vinyl acetate², and acrylonitrile³. Insolubility of the polymer in alcohols and acids does not appear to affect the chain-transfer reaction. This might be attributed to the reaction having been allowed to proceed within 5% monomer conversion.

10. Conant and Wheland, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 1212.

11. Glazebrook and Pearson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1777.

In the case of chlorinated solvents, some interesting results are obtained. It has been generally true for most solvents that the transfer constant for methyl acrylate is consistent with the position of methyl acrylate radical in the radical reactivity series obtained by Mayo and Walling¹², Nozaki *et al.*¹³ and others, viz., $\text{CH}_2 = \text{CH} - \text{O} - \text{COMe} > \text{CH}_2 = \text{CH} - \text{CN} > \text{CH}_2 = \text{CH} - \text{COOMe} > \text{CH}_2 = \text{CHMe} - \text{COOMe} > \text{CH}_2 = \text{CHPh}$. For methyl acrylate polymerisation, the chain-transfer constants in chlorinated solvents are in the order: $\text{CHCl}_3 > \text{CCl}_4 > \text{Cl}_2\text{CH} \cdot \text{CHCl}_2 > \text{Cl} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \text{CH}_2 \text{Cl} > \text{CH}_3\text{CCl}_3$. This is identical with the order observed in the case of acrylonitrile. In the polymerisation of styrene, methyl methacrylate, and vinyl acetate, CCl_4 has a higher transfer than chloroform. The order is reversed in methyl acrylate and also in acrylonitrile. From this it might be inferred that abstraction of tertiary hydrogen in CHCl_3 is preferred in methyl acrylate and acrylonitrile than a Cl atom from CCl_4 . This might not be too surprising if we consider the methyl group in methyl methacrylate to donate electrons, which being further polarised by the C = O linkage of the ester group leads to a positive charge on the α -carbon. This would naturally favour addition of Cl than a proton. In methyl acrylate, the H atom does not give rise to such polarity centres and proton is therefore preferred.

Substitution of the hydrogen atom of chloroform by a methyl group brings about a two- or four-fold decrease in its capacity to serve as a transfer agent in all the monomers. *sym*-Tetrachloroethane has two tertiary hydrogen atoms attached to the two CCl_2 groups, but in methyl acrylate polymerisation as also in acrylonitrile³, methyl methacrylate¹, and vinyl acetate² polymerisation, it affords a lower transfer constant than CHCl_3 . The difference in activity may only be attributed to the difference in the number of halogen atoms linked to the carbon atom carrying the transferable hydrogen. Dichloroethane shows a still further decrease in activity. Chlorobenzene shows a fairly good measure of transfer in the polymerisation of methyl acrylate; it is tentatively assumed that in view of the result recently obtained by Mayo¹⁴, chlorine is not abstracted from the solvent, but that transfer occurs by the intermediate formation of a complex radical with the solvent. This is equivalent to an enhanced rate of monomer transfer, but through a different path.

A situation, different from those discussed above, arises when we consider CCl_4 as the transfer agent. For this solvent, as is shown by the value of transfer constants, the radical reactivity follows the following sequence: vinyl acetate > styrene > methyl methacrylate > methyl acrylate > acrylonitrile. This order is not the same as is recorded in Nozaki's series and the situation has been discussed in a previous communication² from the point of view of stability of the products formed by the transfer reaction. As regards the stability of the products, one need only point out that it is not enough to admit the importance of the stability of the radical product formed from the solvent's fragment. It is also necessary to consider the stability or otherwise of the terminated polymer molecule, as has been pointed out by Pállit *et al.*⁸. It should be interesting to know more fully the reasons why CCl_4 and CHCl_3 behave so differently in the transfer reaction in spite of the facts that (i) the transition states in the two cases look so similar $\text{R} \cdot \cdot \cdot \text{X} \cdot \cdot \cdot \text{CCl}_3$, (ii) the resultant radical is CCl_3 in both the cases, and (iii) the steric factors cannot be very

12. *Faraday Soc. Disc.*, 1947, 2, 285.

13. *Ibid.*, p. 337.

14. Mayo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 6133.

different. The terminated polymer molecule in one case has a newly acquired C—H bond and in the other, a C—Cl bond.

But it is worthwhile looking at the matter from the other point of view, viz., the resonance stabilisation of the transition state depending on the electron-attracting or electron-donating nature of the radicals and the solvents. An analogous situation arises when mercaptans are the transfer agents. Walling's suggestion¹⁵ about the contribution of different electronic structures contributing towards the resonance stabilisation of the transition states with electron-donating radicals, e.g., vinyl acetate and styrene, and the electron-attracting mercaptan molecule is quite plausible. Similar arguments have been advanced by Mesrobian and Fuhrman¹⁶ whose data with CBr_4 run parallel to ours with CCl_4 . This view is further strengthened by the results with tertiary amines as transfer agents, recently reported by Bamford and White¹⁷. Unlike the mercaptans and carbon tetrahalides, tertiary amines are expected to be electron-donating in the transition state. One therefore expects, as indeed is borne out by experimental data, that the reactivity series of the radicals will follow a reverse order in this case: acrylonitrile > methyl acrylate > vinyl acetate > methyl methacrylate > styrene.

In the hydrocarbon solvents, it is generally assumed that the polar factor is the least effective. The trend of the C_s values in chloroform suggests that in this case also, the factors other than polar are predominant. This will be evident from the ratio of transfer constants for chloroform and toluene, recorded for the different monomers in Table IV. For comparison, similar ratios with respect to toluene have been shown for other solvents also.

We notice that with the chain-transfer constants for the solvents CBr_4 and $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{SH}$, where the linking of the bonds broken is comparatively weak, methyl acrylate has a higher C_s value than methyl methacrylate in spite of the polar factors contributing in the opposite direction. This is possibly due to the fact that under the circumstances the steric factor becomes operative in the transfer reaction. The other monomers of course behave normally. In the case of mercaptans, chain transfer takes place as a displacement on a hydrogen atom as in the case of CHCl_3 . Thus the mere fact that in CHCl_3 it is a displacement reaction on hydrogen, whereas in CCl_4 it is on chlorine, does not provide any clue to the problem, since mercaptans and CCl_4 show a similar polarity towards the radicals.

15. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 2561.

16. *Ibid.*, 1954, **76**, 3281.

17. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, **52**, 716.

18. *Makromol. Chem.*, 1955, **17**, 20; *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1958, **11B**, 152.

19. Bamford and Jenkins, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1955, **A228**, 220.

20. Matheson et al., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, (a) 1951, **73**, 5395; (b) 1949, **71**, 497; (c) 1951, **73**, 1700; (d) 1949, **71**, 2610.